

2-Methylpentane-2,4-Dioxysilicon(IV) Complexes of 4-(Alkyl or Aryl)Amino-3-Pentene-2-One

R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, India

Manuscript received 19 September 1978, revised 2 May 1979, accepted 9 July 1980

2-Methylpentane-2,4-dioxysilicon(IV) complexes of the type $\text{Si}(\text{SBH})_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2)$ (where SBH and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ represent the monofunctional bidentate Schiff base and 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol molecules respectively) have been synthesized by the reactions of silicon tetraacetate, monofunctional bidentate Schiff base and 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol in 1 : 2 : 1 molar ratio. The resulting derivatives are non-electrolytes in DMF and monomers in boiling benzene. On the basis of infrared and ^1H NMR spectral studies, suitable structures have been indicated for the resulting new compounds.

A careful survey of the literature revealed that except for a few publications on the β -ketoamine derivatives of silicon with tridentate^{1,2} ligands, systematic studies on other types of β -ketoamine derivatives are lacking. It was, therefore, considered of interest to synthesize some new silicon derivatives of bidentate β -ketoamines and to study their main characteristics.

In previous communications^{3,4} from these laboratories, silicon complexes with the Schiff bases derived from β -diketones and aminoalcohols have been reported. In this paper, the reactions of silicon tetraacetate with the Schiff bases derived from 2, 4-pentanedione and alkyl or arylamines have been discussed. The monofunctional bidentate Schiff bases, and 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol used in the present investigations may be represented by the general structures (I) and (II)

(I)

(II)

(where $\text{R} = -\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, $n\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$, $iso\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$, $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$, $iso\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$, $sec\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$, $tert\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$, $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $o\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$, $o\text{-OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ and $p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$).

Experimental

All the reactions have been carried out under strictly anhydrous conditions. The starting materials were prepared as reported earlier.⁴

Preparation of β -ketoamines :

The β -ketoamines were prepared by taking equimolar amounts of 2, 4-pentanedione and amines in

benzene and refluxing for 4-5 hours. The water formed in the reaction was removed azeotropically with benzene and the resulting products were distilled before use. Their melting or boiling points are as follows :

1. 4-(Ethyl)amino-3-pentene-2-one ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}$), b. p. $165^\circ/7.5$ mm.
2. 4-(*n*-Propyl)amino-3-pentene-2-one ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$), b. p. $77^\circ/0.05$ mm.
3. 4-(*iso*-Propyl)amino-3-pentene-2-one ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$)*. b. p. $85^\circ/3.0$ mm.
4. 4-(*n*-Butyl)amino-3-pentene-2-one ($\text{C}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$), b. p. $68^\circ/0.3$ mm.
5. 4-(*sec*-Butyl)amino-3-pentene-2-one ($\text{C}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$)*, b. p. $62^\circ/0.01$ mm.
6. 4-(*iso*-Butyl)amino-3-pentene-2-one ($\text{C}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$)**, b. p. $82^\circ/0.05$ mm.
7. 4-(*tert*-Butyl)amino-3-pentene-2-one ($\text{C}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$)[‡], b. p. $127^\circ/7.1\text{-}7.2$ mm.
8. 4-(Phenyl)amino-3-pentene-2-one ($\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}$), b. p. $97^\circ/0.2$ mm.
9. 4-(*o*-Chlorophenyl)amino-3-pentene-2-one ($\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{NOCl}$), b. p. $140^\circ/2.0$ mm.
10. 4-(*o*-Methoxyphenyl)amino-3-pentene-2-one ($\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_2$), b. p. $128\text{-}129^\circ/0.7\text{-}0.8$ mm.
11. 4-(*p*-Methylphenyl)amino-3-pentene-2-one ($\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}$), m. p. 58° .

Analytical Methods and Physical Measurements :

Infrared spectra were recorded in the range, $4000\text{-}400$ cm^{-1} with a Perkin-Elmer 557 grating IR

TABLE I—REACTIONS OF SILICON TETRAACETATE WITH SCHIFF BASES AND 2-METHYLPENTANE-2,4-DIOL ($C_6H_{14}O_2$) IN 1 : 2 : 1 MOLAR RATIO

Sl. No.	Si(OAc) ₄ (g)	Schiff base (g)	C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ (g)	Refluxing time (hrs)	Product, yield (g) and characteristics	Acetic acid in	Analysis(%)		Mol. Wt.
						the azeotrope (g)	Si	N	Found
						Found (Calcd)	Found (Calcd)	Found (Calcd)	
1.	1.55	C ₇ H ₁₃ NO (1.49)	0.69	14	Si(C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂)(C ₇ H ₁₃ NO) ₂ , (2.01), yellow viscous liquid, soluble in benzene	1.39 (1.40)	7.02 (7.07)	7.20 (7.06)	410 (396)
2.	1.05	C ₆ H ₁₂ NO (1.12)	0.47	16	Si(C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂)(C ₆ H ₁₂ NO) ₂ , (1.50), brown semi-solid, soluble in benzene	0.94 (0.95)	6.60 (6.61)	6.60 (6.59)	430 (424)
3.	1.37	C ₉ H ₁₆ NO* (1.46)	0.61	17	Si(C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂)(C ₉ H ₁₆ NO) ₂ *, (1.98), yellow semi-solid, soluble in benzene	1.01 (1.24)	6.75 (6.61)	6.50 (6.59)	432 (424)
4.	1.28	C ₉ H ₁₇ NO (1.50)	0.57	15	Si(C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂)(C ₉ H ₁₆ NO) ₂ , (1.88), yellow solid, soluble in benzene	1.09 (1.16)	6.40 (6.20)	6.21 (6.18)	441 (452)
5.	2.00	C ₉ H ₁₇ NO* (2.35)	0.89	16	Si(C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂)(C ₉ H ₁₆ NO) ₂ *, (3.01), brown semi-solid, soluble in benzene	1.80 (1.81)	6.34 (6.20)	6.20 (6.18)	450 (452)
6.	1.98	C ₉ H ₁₇ NO** (2.32)	0.88	18	Si(C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂)(C ₉ H ₁₆ NO) ₂ **, (2.99), yellow semi-solid, soluble in benzene	1.79 (1.80)	6.22 (6.20)	6.30 (6.18)	457 (452)
7.	0.97	C ₉ H ₁₇ NO [‡] (1.14)	0.45	15	Si(C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂)(C ₉ H ₁₆ NO) ₂ [‡] , (1.57), brownish yellow semi-solid, soluble in benzene	0.78 (0.88)	6.54 (6.20)	6.09 (6.18)	472 (452)
8.	1.50	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ NO (1.99)	0.61	20	Si(C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂)(C ₁₁ H ₁₈ NO) ₂ , (2.40), yellow solid, soluble in benzene	1.20 (1.36)	5.71 (5.69)	5.59 (5.68)	482 (492)
9.	1.43	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ NCIO (2.27)	0.63	18	Si(C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂)(C ₁₁ H ₁₈ NCIO) ₂ , (2.84), yellow solid, soluble in benzene	1.30 (1.30)	5.22 (5.00)	5.01 (4.98)	581 (561)
10.	1.73	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ NO ₂ (2.68)	0.77	22	Si(C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂)(C ₁₂ H ₁₈ NO ₂) ₂ , (3.20), yellow semi-solid, soluble in benzene	1.55 (1.57)	5.19 (5.07)	4.99 (5.05)	568 (552)
11.	1.46	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ NO (2.09)	0.65	20	Si(C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂)(C ₁₂ H ₁₈ NO) ₂ , (2.67), yellow solid, soluble in benzene	1.28 (1.32)	5.28 (5.39)	5.45 (5.37)	529 (520)

*, ** and [‡] have been used to distinguish between the compounds of the same molecular formula.

Spectrophotometer as nujol mulls and in some cases as neat liquids. The molecular weights were determined in boiling benzene by means of an ebulliometer (Gallen Kamp) using thermistor sensing. Conductivity measurements were carried out by a conductivity bridge type 235 and the ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in benzene with the help of Perkin-Elmer RB-12 Spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard.

Synthesis of Silicon(IV) β-ketoamine Complexes :

On treating silicon tetraacetate with the ligands, SBH and C₆H₁₄O₂ in 1 : 2 : 1 molar ratios in toluene, a clear solution was obtained. The reaction mixture was refluxed at the bath temperature of ~130° followed by the slow fractionation of the liberated

acetic acid with toluene. It was then estimated against a standard sodium hydroxide solution. The residual toluene was then removed under reduced pressure and the resulting products of the type Si(SB)₂(C₆H₁₄O₂) were finally dried at 50-55°/0.05 mm for 2-3 hours. The details of their analyses and syntheses are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The resulting complexes are coloured liquids, semi-solids or solids and have been found to be soluble in benzene. These are quite stable in the open atmosphere and decompose on being treated with water. Attempts to distil these even under reduced pressure remained unsuccessful.

TABLE 2—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF LIGANDS AND THEIR SILICON COMPLEX IN δ(ppm)

Compound	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i
(I)	1.65	4.65	1.65	3.00	0.90	10.55	—	—	—
(II)	—	—	—	—	—	4.80	1.30	1.90	4.05
(III)	1.87	4.86	1.87	3.20	1.20	—	1.87 ⁺⁺	2.50	4.30

⁺⁺ merged with CH₃, marked with C.

The ebullioscopic determinations of molecular weights in boiling benzene show them to be monomers indicating a hexa-coordinated environment(III) for the central silicon atom in these derivatives.

[Where N-OH and HO-OH represent the SBH and C₆H₄O₂ molecules respectively.]

Conductance :

Low molar conductance values (8-15 ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) for all these complexes in DMF show their non-electrolytic nature.

Infrared Spectra :

The i. r. spectra of the Schiff bases as well as their corresponding silicon complexes have been recorded. On comparing the two spectra, the following points appear to be significant from the point of view of discussion :

In the case of Schiff bases no absorption band appears in the region 3400-3200 cm⁻¹. However, on account of strong hydrogen bonding a broad band is observed in the 3050-2900 cm⁻¹ region. Coordination through oxygen as well as nitrogen

atoms of these groups can be inferred by the absence of any band due to νOH or νNH. This type of bonding is also substantiated by the appearance of a number of new bands of medium intensity in the region 700-600 cm⁻¹ and these may be assigned to νSi-O.⁵

A strong band is observed in the region 1615-1595 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the Schiff bases and this is a characteristic absorption band of the azomethine group (>C=N). In the i.r. spectra of silicon complexes of Schiff bases, ν(C=N) is observed at almost the same position.

¹H NMR Spectral Studies :

The ¹H NMR spectra of 4-(ethylamino)-3-pentene-2-one (i), 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol (ii) and their corresponding silicon complex (iii) have been recorded in benzene. The chemical shift values (δ) of the different protons are recorded in Table 2.

The comparison of the two spectra leads to the following conclusion and this is in conformity with the proposed structures of the silicon complexes :

1. The ¹H NMR spectra show preference for the Ketamine structure over other equilibrium forms for compound (i) as well as for the Schiff bases derived by the condensation of β-diketones with alkyl or aryl amines or diamines as reported earlier^{6,7,8}.

2. The 10.55 δ peak due to the hydrogen bonded NH protons of the ligand (i) disappears in compound (iii) and this indicates the chelating nature of the ligand and coordination of nitrogen to silicon.

3. The bonding of alcoholic oxygen in the compound (iii) is substantiated by the disappearance of OH proton signal which is observed at 4.80 δ in the ligand (ii).

4. The proton signals of the amine residue of the ligand moiety are shifted downfield in the spectrum of the silicon complex (iii) and this may further be due to the formation of a coordinate bond between nitrogen and silicon causing a change in the electronic environment around the above protons.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R. V. S.) is grateful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the financial assistance.

References

1. R. C. MEHROTRA, *Pure & Appl. Chem.*, 1966, **13**, 124.
2. L. V. ORLOVA, A. D. GARNOVSKII, O. A. OSIPOV and I. I. KUKUSHKINA, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1968, **38**, 1850.
3. R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 84.
4. R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 764.
5. W. E. NEWTON and D. W. H. RANKIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 2664.
6. G. W. EVERETT, Jr. and R. H. HOLM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 2117.
7. N. M. D. BROWN and D. C. NONHEBEL, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, **24**, 5658.
8. G. O. DUDEK and G. VOLFF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 2697.